

DODS Programmer's Guide
The Client and Server Toolkit
Version 1.6

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July 20, 2002

Preface

This document describes how to use the Distributed Oceanographic Data System toolkit software to build both DODS data servers and client-libraries. Using the objects and functions contained in the toolkit, you can create programs to serve data over the internet as well as programs that can request data from any DODS server.

This document covers release 3.2 and later of the DODS software.

0.1 Who is this Guide for?

This guide is for people who wish to use the Distributed Oceanographic Data System software to write a new DODS data server, or a new client library. Typically, this will only be those people who wish to serve data in a format that is not currently supported by the DODS team, or who have an existing application that uses an idiosyncratic or unusual API for data access. Most users will be able to use one of the already written servers or client libraries. See the *The DODS User Guide* for a list of these.

To write a new client or server, you may want to refer to other DODS documents as well as this one. The *Writing an OPeNDAPServer* and the *Writing an OPeNDAPClient* tutorials offer step-by-step instruction. And the *The DODS Toolkit Reference* contains the detailed descriptions of the classes omitted for space reasons from this document.

This documentation assumes that the readers are competent C++ programmers, and are familiar with networked applications, and the POSIX programming environment.

Because the type of information presented in a document like this depends to a large extent on the needs of its readers we welcome your feedback and comments. In particular, if you have any questions about individual sections, email those questions and we'll send back an answer as well as including that information in the next version of this document. Send queries to: support@unidata.ucar.edu.

0.2 Organization of this Document

This Guide is divided into five chapters.

Chapter 1 provides background information on the organization of the toolkit software.

Chapter 2 describes how to use the Network I/O classes to manage virtual connections.

Chapter 3 discusses how to sub-class the toolkit C++ classes so that they are specialized for your specific use.

Chapter 4 describes in detail how to write certain sections of both the data server and the client-library for a new API.

Chapter 5 describes how to link user programs with the new client-library implementation of an API.

0.3 Conventions

The typographic conventions shown in Table 1 are followed in this guide and all the other DODS documentation.

Table 1: Typographic Conventions

Literal text	Typed by the computer, or in a code listing.
<i>User input</i>	Type this precisely as written.
<i>Variables</i>	Used as a place holder for a user-specified or variable value. Choose an appropriate value and use that in place.
Button Text	Used to indicate text on a GUI button.
Menu Name	This is the name of a GUI menu.

When referring to a button in a menu, we will often use the notation:

Menu,Button. For example, **Options,Colors,Foreground** would indicate the **Foreground** button in the **Colors** menu, selected under the **Options** menu.

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The DODS Client and Server Toolkit

The Distributed Oceanographic Data System (DODS) is a system used to facilitate access to scientific data on the internet. Using DODS, you can turn any data analysis program that uses one of several data access APIs into a powerful, internet-friendly data browser. For basic information about the structure of DODS and its components, please see *The DODS User Guide*.

You are probably reading this volume because you are considering writing either a DODS (OPeNDAP) server or client. In this case, you will also want to peruse the *Writing an OPeNDAPClient* or *Writing an OPeNDAPServer* tutorials, which contain step-by-step instructions for doing so. This guide will be useful to explain why steps are necessary, and some of the theory of operation of DODS.

The DODS Toolkit software consists of a collection of C++ classes used to build DODS data servers and clients:

Type classes A complete implementation of the DODS data access protocol (DAP). This consists of a set of virtual classes for different types of data, which must be sub-classed to use.

Data classes This is a set of classes, including both the Data Descriptor Structure (*DDS*) and the Data Attribute Structure (*DAS*), designed to contain information about a dataset's data.

Connect classes These classes are used by a DODS client to mimic a durable connection to a DODS server.

DODSFilter This class consists of several utility functions useful for writing DODS servers.

CGI Utilities The file `cgi_util.h` describes a small number of other common functions needed by DODS servers.

The DAP toolkit contains three class hierarchies: one for each of the *DAS* and *DDS* objects, rooted in classes with those names, and one for the variables, rooted at the class *BaseType*. The following sections present an overview of these class hierarchies and describe, in general terms, how they are used to build the client-library and data server. See Section 1.1 on page 3 for information about the *DDS* and *DAS* classes. To use the type classes, they must be subclassed. Chapter 3 provides a detailed description of this process.

Detailed information about the *DAS* and *DDS* themselves is available in the *The DODS User Guide*. Descriptions of the classes and their member functions are in the reference material in the *The DODS Toolkit Reference*.

The DODS toolkit also contains two classes used by DODS clients to manage network connections between themselves and a server. The *Connect* object manages a single connection with some DODS server, and the *Connections* object manages a group of *Connect* objects. The *Connect* class is meant to be subclassed when used by a real client library. See Chapter 2.

1.1 The *DAS* and *DDS* Objects

The dataset attribute structure (*DAS*: page 4) and dataset descriptor structure (*DDS*: page 8) objects are used to store information about a data set's variables. These objects are used on both the client and server sides, although there are class features that only pertain to one or another of the roles. They can be thought of as metadata objects. In this book, however, we will avoid the term *metadata* because often this is *data* to many users.

It might be said that neither the *DAS* nor the *DDS* contain actual science data — the *DAS* contains attribute information from the data set while the *DDS* contains structural information about the data set and variables in the data set. Since the boundary between data and metadata (or data attributes) is often a blurry one, this is not a distinction we will insist on.

To build both the *DAS* and *DDS*, the server either reads information directly from the dataset or from DODS-specific *ancillary data* files, depending on the capabilities of the data access API used to access the data. The *DAS* and *DDS* server *filter* programs do this and then transmit the resulting object to the client.

On the client side, the DODS client¹ uses information in the *DAS* and *DDS* to satisfy API calls issued by the user program requesting information about variables, their type, shape, and attributes. The client requests both of these objects when it first contacts the remote data set. The *DAS* and *DDS* objects are then stored as part of a *virtual connection* to that data set and can be used repeatedly by the client library without retransmission.

The *DAS* and *DDS* objects have both an internal and an external representation. Internal to the DODS client or server, these structures are stored as C++ objects, while their external representation is as text. The object is sent from the server to the client using this text representation. Each of the two classes contains a parser which can read the text representation and recreate the object's internal representation. In addition, it is possible to write the text representation for either object (using a text editor) and then use the parser to create the internal, C++, object. Furthermore, the text representation is a type of persistence and can be used to build a flexible object caching mechanism.

One possible use for this caching mechanism is to store the *DAS* and *DDS* for a dataset and use the stored versions in place of opening the data set and reading information about it and its contents. For large data sets with many variables this can result in a significant performance improvement, and several of the packaged DODS servers use it.

The caching mechanism may also be used on the server-side to store extra information about the data set—information that is not present in the data set

¹Whatever it is. The DODS client can be another server, a user application linked with a DODS-compliant API, or a standalone program using the DODS data access protocol API. In any case, the use of the class libraries described in this document is identical.

proper, but which the data provider would like included when people access the data set via DODS. In this scenario, the data server first integrates the data set file(s) using the API and builds the *DAS* and *DDS*. Once an initial version of the *DAS* and *DDS* are resident in memory, the parser is used to read an external text file which contains additions to, or corrections of, the information extracted from the data file. This information is the ancillary data introduced above. Several of the DODS servers use this mechanism.

1.1.1 The *DAS* Object

The *DAS* contains attribute information that is generally *not* used by software when processing the variables; this object is specifically designed to hold all the information in a data set that has no where else to go. Each variable can have an unlimited number of attributes. There are also ‘global’ attributes that apply to the dataset as a whole. Each attribute is a set of three elements: the attribute name, type and value. The supported types for an attribute are: Byte, Int32, Float64, String and URL, and vectors of these types. These types have the same range of values as the corresponding types in the data access protocol.

A variable’s attributes can be any qualities that are not part of the *DDS*. Thus, the type and shape of a variable are *not* attributes; they are characteristics of the variable and are part of the *DDS* (see Section 1.1.2). However, users may store any other information as attributes², including paragraphs of text, vectors of integers and floating point values, and so on. There are some standard attributes required by the DODS standard. The system *could* work without these attributes, but they are required anyway to make other aspects of the systems work better.

Many APIs support the concept of information in the data set that is not structured, and provide function calls to access that information. The *DAS* object provides a place for all that information. The data server can interrogate the data set and build the *DAS* and the client-library can use the *DAS* object to satisfy many of the API calls requesting information about the variables in a data set.

Figure 1.1 is a diagram of the *DAS* object. The *DAS* consists of the following components:

- A list of attribute tables, each of which is a list of attributes for a particular data variable. Since data variables can contain other data variables (as with a compound data type, for example), an attribute table can contain other attribute tables.
- A parser and scanner to read a text version of the *DAS* object and create the corresponding C++ (binary) representation in memory.
- A printer with which you can create a text version of the *DAS* object.

²Actually, there is no reason that type, etc. cannot be stored as an attribute; however, it must be in the *DDS* regardless

Figure 1.1: A *DAS* Object

The *DAS* printer (`DAS::print()`) is used to create a textual representation of the C++ object. The object is transmitted from server to client using this representation. The scanner and parser (`DAS::parse()`) reads the printed representation and creates a C++ object to match this specification. This object method can be used to read the text version from a disk or from a network connection, depending on the input stream identified for it.

The third part of the *DAS*, the attribute table list, points to a series of *attribute tables*. An attribute table is a list of name-type-value triples used to describe a data variable. Each attribute describes some aspect of the data variable. The example list in figure 1.2 shows what a table might look like for one of the data variables in figure 1.1. (The types have been left out of the diagrams for clarity.)

The *DAS* object contains member functions to add or retrieve *AttrTable* objects as well as individual attributes based on a variable name. In addition, the *AttrTable* object may be traversed using a *Pix*³.

The value of an attribute can itself be another attribute table. So, for example, an aggregate variable that contains other variables, such as a Structure, might have an attribute table for each of its member variables. In figure 1.3, you can see illustrated the attributes of an aggregate data variable. The first three attributes apply to the collection of data (it was taken with a CTD instrument, from the good ship R/V Endeavour, and so on), while the next three attributes reveal attributes of the constituent data variables. Each of the values of these attributes is itself an attribute table, containing attribute data about that data type.

³A *Pix* is a “pseudoindex” object. See the libstdc++ documentation for more information.

Figure 1.2: An Attribute Table

Figure 1.3: A Nested Attribute Table

DODS attribute tables are modelled with the *AttrTable* class. Each *AttrTable* object contains a doubly-linked list of attribute triples, of a structure named **entry**. Each entry object contains a Name, Type and vector of values. *AttrTable* provides methods for reading, writing, and modifying the attribute table.

The DODS definition of dataset attributes contains a “Global” attribute. This has nothing to do with the data structure of the *DAS* object, but with its use in DODS. Global attributes apply to all the variables in the dataset. They can also be thought of as being attributes of the dataset itself.

1.1.2 The *DDS* Object

The *DDS* is used to store information about the organization of the data set and its variables. It contains information about the type and shape of variables. While the *DDS* is similar to the *DAS* in that it is used to store information about the data set, it is used quite differently by both the client and server components of DODS. The *DAS* is a stand-alone object and is used solely for the purpose of storing attributes of variables and the dataset. The *DDS*, however, stores type information about a data set's variables by storing actual instances of those variables.

The DODS data access protocol variable objects have methods that can be used to read values from a data set or transfer the variable's value over the network. This makes it convenient to use the *DDS* object itself to hold data, and on the server side, the *DDS* object is used by both the *DDS* filter program and the data filter program. (See Section 4.1 on page 29 for more information about the structure of the DODS server.)

Figure 1.4: The *DDS* Object

Figure 1.4 shows the structure of the *DDS* class objects. The *DDS* consists of the following components:

- A *String* object used to store the name of the dataset to which this *DDS* refers.
- A singly-linked list to store the variables in the data set. Each variable is stored in an instance of one of the *BaseType* class's descendants, and can be a simple or compound data type.
- A “printer” method to create a textual representation of the *DDS*. Among other uses, this is used to transmit the *DDS* from server to client.
- A parser and scanner to read a text *DDS* and convert it into its C++ form. This is used to read *DDS* information from a disk, and also to receive it over the network.
- A singly-linked list of parsed constraint expression clauses. The clauses wait here to be evaluated.
- A constraint expression parser and scanner to extract constraint expression clauses from the input constraint expression. This component is responsible for creating the list of constraint expression clauses.

The *DDS* object provides methods to access and operate each of these components. The two lists can be traversed with a g++ *Pix* object.

The *DDS* is ‘lexically scoped’ so that two *Structure* variables may have components with the same names; each component will be referred to using the *Structure* name and the dot operator. So for example, if a *DDS* called **ralph** contains two structures, **vitals** and **new_hip**, and each structure contains a variable called **age**, you can differentiate the two by referring to one as **ralph.vitals.age** and the other as **ralph.new_hip.age**.

1.2 The Type Hierarchy

The *Type Hierarchy* is the set of classes that form the hierarchy used to build objects that contain data. These classes comprise the data model for DODS. They contain *simple* data types such as integer and floating point values as well as *compound* types like structure and sequence. Each type is embodied by a C++ class, and the classes are arranged in a class hierarchy, with a *BaseType* defining properties inherited by all the type classes.

This section contains a brief description of the different types, their relation to one another, and how they are used in an application program. For detailed descriptions of the characteristics of each type, including inheritance diagrams, please see the *The DODS Toolkit Reference*.

The DODS types can be divided into four categories:

- *BaseType*
- Simple Types
Byte Int16 UInt16 Int32 UInt32 Float32 Float64 Str Url
- Vector Types
List Array
- Compound Types
Structure Sequence Grid

Unlike the other classes in the DODS toolkit, the type classes are abstract classes—in order to be used by a program, you must subclass the hierarchy and create concrete classes to instantiate.

1.2.1 Common Ancestor: BaseType

The root of the type hierarchy is the abstract class *BaseType*. This class, because it is abstract, is never instantiated itself. *BaseType* is used as the base class for all of the different types of variables, and contains common member functions used by all the other type classes. For simple variables such as *Int32*, only the abstract virtual functions in *BaseType* need to be added to complete the class definition. Compound types like *Structure* usually require more. A compound type contains one or more instances of *BaseType*, and requires methods to access, add and remove these member variables.

1.2.2 Simple Types

The DODS simple data types consist of *Byte*, *Int16*, *UInt16*, *Int32*, *UInt32*, *Float32*, *Float64*, *Str* and *Url*. These data types match very closely the corresponding types in C or Fortran. Note that—internally—each of these types uses either the C or C++ representation to hold the value of the object.

These abstract classes are direct descendents of *BaseType* which contain only their definitions for *BaseType*'s abstract member functions and a single constructor.

Byte Variables which store bytes. Equivalent to unsigned char on most UNIX workstations.

Int16 Variables which store integer values as 16-bit twos-complement signed integers. Equivalent to `int` on most 16-bit UNIX workstations.

UInt16 Unsigned integer. A 16-bit unsigned integer value.

Int32 Variables which store integer values as 32-bit twos-complement signed integers. Equivalent to `int` on most 32-bit UNIX workstations.

UInt32 Unsigned integer. A 32-bit unsigned integer value.

Float32 Variables which store floating point data. Defined as the IEEE 32-bit floating point data type, equivalent to a `float` in ANSI C.

Float64 Variables which store floating point data. Defined as the IEEE 64-bit floating point data type, equivalent to a `double` in ANSI C.

Str Variables which store string information. A DODS string is *not* a sequence of characters referenced using a pointer (as it is in C), it is represented using a C++ object of the class *String*.

Url Variables which store references to network resources. This is a sub-class of *Str*.

1.2.3 Vector Types: Array, List

The vector data types are *Array* and *List*. A *List* is a simple ordering of elements of a single type. An *Array* arranges the elements so that they can be easily accessed with one or more indices.

Array Instances of *Array* have different semantics than arrays in C. They are multi-dimensional data structures which contain *N* instances of some data type. Each instance in the array can be referred to by an integer index between 0 and *N-1*. Multidimensional arrays are declared using C's syntax of a sequence of bracketed integer values: `Int32 a[10][20]` declares an array of 10 arrays of 20 integers. However, unlike C arrays, the *Array* class

supports named dimensions. In the preceding example, the array could have been declared: `Int32 a[row = 10][col = 20]` where `row` and `col` are the names of the first and second dimension, respectively. You can use the `dimension_name` and `dimension_size` member functions of the *Array* class to determine the name and size for the i^{th} dimension.

Array, like all of the compound types, contains a reference to a component variable. In the preceding example, the instance of *Array* would contain information about the dimensions of the array (10 by 20), but not the type of the elements (`Int32`). The element type information is stored in the component variable which the instance of *Array* references.

When creating an array, the dimension sizes (and optionally their names) must be set. Regardless of the shape of the array, it is always stored as a vector. In order to access the element of a multidimensional array it is necessary to calculate the offset for a given element.

List A *List* is an ordered collection of elements of unknown length. This is in contrast to the *Array*, whose size is always known in advance. When a *List* type is declared no size information is supplied, but in order to transmit a *List* object the length of that list must be known. Thus, internally the number of elements in the current value *is* stored.

1.2.4 Compound Types: Structure, Sequence, Function, Grid

The compound data types are used to build new types as aggregates of other types, including other compound types. (Note that *List* and *Array* are compound types, as well, but contain only a single type of data.) *Structure*, *Sequence* and *Function* all contain a list of *BaseType* objects. However, they have different semantics; a *Structure* is a simple aggregate; nothing other than aggregation is implied, while *Sequence* and *Function* define templates for relational objects. A *Grid* combines several *Array* objects so that nonlinear values may be applied to the indices of an array.

Structure A *Structure* is an ordered collection of variables that conveys no relational information other than grouping. The variables that are members of a *Structure* may be of different types. In addition to the (possible) benefit of added organization, *Structure* may be used to supply information to the system that may be useful in optimizing the access or translation operations.

Sequence A *Sequence* is similar to a *Structure* in that it consists of an ordered collection of variables which may be of different types. However, where an instance of a *Structure* object describes a single set of data variables, an instance of a *Sequence* object describes a set of data variables, each of which is an entry in an ordered series of similar data variables.

Consider a *Sequence* named *S*, where each instance is called *s*:

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 s_{00} & s_{01} & \cdots & s_{0n} \\
 s_{10} & s_{11} & \cdots & s_{1n} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\
 s_{i0} & s_{i1} & \cdots & s_{in} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots
 \end{array}$$

Every instance s_i of S has the same number, order, and class of variables. A *Sequence* implies that each of the n variables is related to each other in some logical way. Because a *Sequence* has several values for each of its variables it has an implied *state*, or position in the sequence, in addition to the instance data values.

Table 1.1: Table of relational data.

Name	Age	Weight
James	32	165
Charlie	7	65.4
Bob	10	80

For example given the the information in Table 1.1, s_0 is **James, 32, 165**, s_1 is **Charlie, 7, 65.4, ...**. The data in the table might have the following Sequence declaration:

```

Sequence {
    Str name;
    Int32 age;
    Float64 weight;
} people;

```

Grid A *Grid* is an association of an N dimensional *Array* with N named vectors (*map vectors*), each of which has the same number of elements as the corresponding dimension of the *Array*. Each vector is used to map indices of one of the *Array*'s dimensions to a set of values which are normally non-integral (e.g., floating point values). Two map vectors may be members of different classes.

In figure 1.5, the grid element indicated by `Grid[2][3]` corresponds to $N[2]$ and $M[3]$, or $N = 92.3$ and $M = 3.9$ respectively. The element has a value of 29.7.

M =	1.2	1.4	1.8	3.9	4.5	
Grid =	32.0	31.5	31.1	30.8	29.2	N= 67.8
	32.3	31.8	31.4	30.9	29.8	68.7
	32.9	32.3	31.8	29.7	30.2	92.3
	32.3	31.8	31.5	30.7	29.9	95.2

Figure 1.5: A sample Grid.

2

Managing Connections

Because DODS uses a communication protocol (http) that does not maintain state information about the link between two processes, these connections are virtual, and all the information about them is maintained by the client. The toolkit contains two classes to help clients manage connections to one or more DODS servers. One class, *Connect* stores information used when a connection is established. It also allows a program to provide local access to data (without a DODS data server).

The second network class of the DODS Toolkit, *Connections*, manages instances of the *Connect* class. It provides a mechanism for the client libraries to pass back to user programs the type of object (such as `int`, opaque pointer, ...) they expect and then to use one of those objects to access the correct instance of *Connect*. *Connections* is a template class. That is, a client library uses the *Connections* class to make an array of some sub-class of *Connect*.

2.1 Connect

The *Connect* class manages one connection to either a remote data set, via a DODS data server, or a local access. For each data set or file that the user program opens, there must be exactly one instance of *Connect*. Because information needed for local access is stored in an instance of *Connect*, this class may also be used (sub-classed) for each client API that needs to maintain additional information about the connection.¹ In the API-specific child of *Connect* additional members can be added to store state information that the client-library needs to maintain the virtual connection (See Section 3.2 for more information on making virtual connections).

Figure 2.1: The Connect Class

The *Connect* class is illustrated in figure 2.1. These objects contain the following information:

URL The URL with which the client library opens the connection with the DODS server.

DDS The *DDS* of the opened dataset. This must be retrieved from the dataset.

DAS The *DAS* of the opened dataset. This must be retrieved from the dataset.

Gui The *Gui* object indicates a graphical widget on the client platform that displays information about the data transfer in progress.

Error The *Error* object contains information used to help the client process an error message from the server.

The *Connect* class provides member functions to get the dataset's *DAS*, *DDS* and data. The instance of *Connect* (or a subclass of *Connect*) stores the URL as the user provides it.

¹For example, the subclasses *JGConnect* and *NCCConnect* exist for JGOFS and NetCDF, respectively.

When the client library receives a URL via its “open” call (which will not actually be called `open` but performs the function of opening a file or data set; e.g., NetCDF’s `ncopen`) it passes that URL to the *Connect* member functions like `request_das` and `request_dds`. These member functions append an appropriate extension (`.das` and `.dds`, for example) onto the URL and retrieve the resulting information from the server, the *DAS* or *DDS* for the dataset.

If you are re-implementing an API and must support function calls that modify how data is accessed (e.g., by creating array slices or by choosing one of a set of variables), then you will need to translate those requests into a DODS constraint expression. You would then pass these synthesized constraint expressions to the `Connect::request_data` member function. (See Section 4.3 on page 45 for more information about constraint expressions.)

The specialized version of *Connect* is the place to put state information needed by a recoded API or other client. This can be used, for example, to emulate an API that maintains a list of open files.

2.2 Connections

The class *Connections* is used to manage a set of instances of the class *Connect* by providing a means to map an index or opaque pointer to an instance of *Connect*.

When a new instance of *Connect* (or a descendent of *Connect*; See Section 3.2) is created, it is added to the *Connections* object using the `add_connect` member function. `add_connect` returns an integer that can be used to access that instance of *Connect* at any time. Similarly, when an instance of *Connect* is to be deleted, the object can be referred to via the *Connections* object and this index.

3

Using the DODS Library Classes

In order to be used by real client-libraries and data servers, many of the classes in the DODS toolkit must be subclassed. For example, the Type Hierarchy classes, which represent the data types in the DODS data model, are all abstract classes. In order to use them in a program they must be subclassed. The *Connect* class also must be subclassed if it to hold additional information about the connection.

3.1 Sub-classing the Type Hierarchy

In order to link a program with the DODS Toolkit library, the DAP's abstract classes must be subclassed and those subclasses must ensure that all of the member functions of those classes have valid definitions. This is necessary because of C++'s rules governing abstract classes. The next three sections cover sub-classing the simple, vector and compound classes, respectively. In addition, a sample set of classes (called the **Test** classes because they are used by the DAP tests) is included with the DAP distribution. You can read the source code for those classes to find out how they were created.

Each of the sub-classed types must supply:

- A constructor that takes a *String* argument and returns an object with that name.
- A virtual destructor.
- A copy function called `ptr_duplicate`.
- The `read` function, to read data from a disk and load it into the type class object.

The `ptr_duplicate` member function returns a pointer to a new instance of the type of object from which it was invoked. This member function exists so that objects that are referenced through pointers to *BaseType* can correctly copy themselves. (If you were to use the operator `new` to copy an object referenced through *BaseType*, you would get a *BaseType*, not a new instance of the type of the referenced object.) Note that `ptr_duplicate` is a virtual function so an object which is a descendent of *BaseType* will get the most specific definition of that function.

The `read` function is much more complicated to write than `ptr_duplicate`, and the difficulty varies depending on the data type to be read. However, this function is only used on the server side of the system and not by the client. That is, it can be implemented with a null function body if all you are building is a client library. The `read` function takes two arguments, the dataset name, and an error flag. It must read from that dataset the values specified by the current constraint expression. The error flag is passed by reference so that `read` can set its value and callers can test it. The class *BaseType* contains a number of member functions to facilitate writing a read function. The return value of `read` is `TRUE` if there is more data to be read (by additional calls to `read`) or `FALSE` otherwise.

3.1.1 Sub-classing the Simple Types

Creating a read function for the simple type classes is a fairly straightforward operation. Simply read the function using the data access API's standard protocol, and use the type class's `val2buf` function to load the data into the type object.

The following function is taken from the DODS implementation of the NetCDF data access library. (See the file `src/nc-dods/NCByte.cc`.)

```

1 NCByte::read(const String &dataset, int &error)
2 {
3     int varid;           /* variable Id */
4     nc_type datatype;   /* variable data type */
5     long cor[MAX_NC_DIMS]; /* corner coordinates */
6     int num_dim;        /* number of dim. in variable */
7     long nels = -1;     /* number of elements in buffer */
8     int id;
9
10    if (read_p()) // already done
11        return true;
12
13    int ncid = lncopen(dataset, NC_NOWRITE); /* netCDF id */
14
15    if (ncid == -1) {
16        cerr << "ncopen failed on " << dataset << endl;
17        return false;
18    }
19
20    varid = lncvarid( ncid, name());
21    (void)lncvarinq( ncid, varid, (char *)0, &datatype,
22                  &num_dim, (int *)0, (int *)0);
23
24    if(nels == -1){
25        for (id = 0; id < num_dim; id++)
26            cor[id] = 0;
27    }
28
29    if (datatype == NC_BYTE){
30        dods_byte Dbyte;
31
32        (void) lncvarget1 (ncid, varid, cor, &Dbyte);
33        set_read_p(true);
34
35        val2buf( &Dbyte );
36
37        (void) lncclose(ncid);
38        return true;
39    }
40    return false;
41 }

```

The following points are worth consideration about the above example.

line 10 Check to see if this variable has already been read.

line 13 The `lncopen()` function call is simply the `ncopen()` function from the NetCDF library. Also, the `lncvarid` function is renamed `ncvarid` and so on. The names have been changed to avoid link-time problems. (Remember that the whole point of this exercise is to create a new `ncopen()` function and its friends.

line 33 This sets the flag tested with the `read_p` function.

line 35 This command transfers values from the dataset's variable to the DODS instance. This is the point where the read actually happens.

Note the use of `dods.byte` in the code example. The DODS configuration process creates definitions for the simple data types like this one. They are stored in `config_dap.h`.

The `read` member function is used by the constraint expression evaluator to extract data from a dataset during evaluation of the constraint expression. This is particularly important to remember because the `read` member function for a simple data type will be called when reading an aggregate type such as *Structure*.

3.1.2 Sub-classing the Vector Types

The vector data types require the same abstract member functions be defined as the simple types. The definition for `ptr_duplicate` is also the same for vector as for simple types. However, the `read` member function for the vector types (classes *Array* and *List*) is more complicated than for the simple types because vectors of values are represented in two ways in DODS, depending on the type of variable in the vector. Arrays are stored as C would store them for the simple types such as *Byte*, *Int32* and *Float64*. However, compound types are stored as arrays of the DODS C++ objects (with the exception of arrays themselves, but more on that later).

When reading an array of *Byte* values, the `val2buf` member function should be passed a pointer to values stored in a contiguous piece of memory. For example, when `read` is called to read a variable `byte-array`, it must determine how much memory to allocate to hold that much information, use `new` to allocate an adequate amount of memory, use the dataset's API calls to read `byte-array` into the newly allocated memory and then pass that memory to `val2buf`. This same procedure can be followed for all the simple types.

However, when reading an array of *Structure*, for example, the values must be stored in the DODS *Array* object one at a time using the *Array* member function `set_vec`. An *Array* object containing a 3x4 array of *Structure* objects will actually point to 12 different instances of that class. An *Array* object containing *Byte* objects contains only one instance of the *Byte* class, as a template for the array elements.

Arrays in DODS are unlike arrays in C in that an array object may have more than one dimension. In terms of the way a value is stored, however, an Array is a single dimensional object. When an Array is declared as having two or more dimensions, those are mapped onto a single vector. To access the element A_{ij} of array A , you must know the size of the first dimension, I , and use the expression $i * I + j$ to compute the offset into the vector.

Since the class *List* is a single dimension array without *declared* size (the size of each value of the List object is stored in the object) the rules for *Array*'s read member function apply.

3.1.3 Sub-classing the Compound Types

The `read` member function of the compound data types simply iterates over the contained variables calling their `read` member functions. In the future, this definition will move into the supplied classes (That is, `read` will no longer be a abstract member function for the compound types.).

The two constructor types *Sequence* and *Function* are different from all the other types in the DAP in that they have *state*. That is, the value of a sequence depends on how many values have been read previously. This is very different from an array where the i^{th} element has the same value regardless of what has happened before. When you write implementations for `read` in the *Sequence* and *Function* classes, you must be sure to write those member functions so that they can be called repeatedly and that each call to read returns the next value of the corresponding data Sequence or Function.

This is true because the constraint expression evaluator must be able to apply certain constraints to values of individual sequence elements and is actually implemented in the DDS class by first calling the read member function, evaluating the constraint expression based on the values and, if they constraint expression is satisfied, calling the serialize member function. See the member function `DDS::send` (See section 4.3.1 for more information on evaluation of constraint expressions).

If, for some reason, it is not possible to write `read` so that it gets called once for each sequence value¹, then you must re-implement `DDS::send` so that its functions are performed. For example, you could implement `Sequence::read` so that the entire sequence is read in and overload `Sequence::serialize` and `Sequence::deserialize` so that the next set of values are sent/received. You would then build a send that called the `Sequence::read` member function once and extracted each successive value, evaluated the constraint expression using on that value and used the result of that evaluation to determine whether to send the value or not.

¹A single entry in a sequence, modelled as a row in a relational table, is sometimes called an instance of the sequence. This is useful terminology, but is occasionally confusing when we are also talking about instances of objects.

3.2 Sub-classing the *Connect* Class

The DODS API defines a connection-less protocol in which a server keeps no information for a client in between data requests. This is in contrast to most data access APIs, which maintain state information about the files or datasets that a user program currently has open. To simulate an API's connection, the client library for that API must create a *virtual connection* using information about the data set it has read from the server. That is, the client library must maintain the *illusion* of a connection (state) for each open data object (typically a file) even though no such connection actually exists.

DODS provides the *Connect* class to make this a simple process. This class contains a variety of information about a dataset and its location on the internet, including the dataset's URL. Most of the information necessary to fake a connection is contained here.

Data access APIs differ widely however, and it is usually necessary to add some information to the *Connect* class to make a workable virtual connection. This information can be stored in the subclassed *Connect*. The API's "open" call must be completely recoded so that the *DAS* and *DDS* objects, as well as any other information, are requested from the dataset server and stored locally in whatever form is most convenient.

Figure 3.1 shows the sub-class of *Connect* used to store information extracted from the *DAS* and *DDS* objects (for the NetCDF library), and used to simulate the storage of information in the original API.²

The private data added to the *Connect* object with this class is as follows:

- `_ncid` This is only used for access to local files. It is the NetCDFfile descriptor, or file ID.
- `_nvars` The number of variables in data file.
- `_ndims` The number of dimensions found. Note that not all the variables in a NetCDFfile have the same number or set of dimensions. This number is the list of all the different ones.
- `_dim_name [MAX_NC_DIMS]` The names of the dimensions found in the data file.
- `_dim_size [MAX_NC_DIMS]` An array containing the size of each dimension found.
- `_das_loc [MAX_NC_VARS]` An index into a table of attributes.

²The NetCDF client library has been rewritten a couple of times since these examples were taken from it. Most of the changes involve additional functionality not necessary for the illustrations here. We have also removed some error-checking to make the intention clearer. Therefore the actual code in the NetCDFsoftware may not match these examples. However, these examples will work.

```
class NCCConnect: public Connect {
private:
    int _ncid;
    int _nvars;
    int _ndims;
    String _dim_name[MAX_NC_DIMS];
    int _dim_size[MAX_NC_DIMS];
    int _das_loc[MAX_NC_VARS];
    void init_list(int i);
    void parse_array_dims();
    void parse_grid_dims();

public:
    NCCConnect(const String &name, const int mode);
    ~NCCConnect();

    int &ncid();
    int ndims();
    int nvars();
    int dim_size(const int dimid);
    const String &dim_name(const int dimid);
    int das_loc(const int varid);
    void parse_das_loc();
    void parse_dims();
};
```

Figure 3.1: The subclass of *Connect* used with the NetCDF client library.

This additional data allows the client library to emulate most of the NetCDF query functions properly and *locally*.

Now look at the recoded open call of the NetCDFlibrary in figure 3.2. The new function has exactly the same type as the original implementation; it takes the same number and type of arguments and returns the same type. The first operation performed by the new open call is to create a *Connect* object (actually an *NCCConnect* object) using the arguments passed to the open call.

After the open call creates the new *NCCConnect* object, it makes sure that the user is not trying to open the remote dataset for writing and, if they are not, reads the *DAS* and *DDS* from the dataset. Once read, the *DAS* and *DDS* objects are parsed using *NCCConnect*'s member functions `parse_das_loc` and `parse_dims`. These two member functions, along with the additional state variables in *NCCConnect*, effectively create the virtual connection. Subsequent calls to the client library for information about the variables (e.g., their size, names, etc.) will be answered using information stored in the symbol table in the *NCCConnect* object.

```

int
ncopen(const char *path, int cmode)
{
    int id;
    NCCConnect *c = new NCCConnect(path);

    if(cmode != NC_NOWRITE) {
        delete c;
        return(-1);
    }

    c->request_das();
    c->request_dds();

    c->parse_das_loc();
    c->parse_dims();

    return(conns.add_connect(c)) ;
}

```

Figure 3.2: The recoded open call of NetCDF.

The code above checks to see whether the user is trying to open a connection for writing. Since DODS is a read-only protocol, this attempt must fail.

4

Using the Toolkit

This chapter describes how to use the toolkit software to build new client libraries and data servers. Before beginning to build either part of a new DODS application, it is very important to be intimate with the details of the API to be replaced.

To create a client library that can *replace* the original API implementation at *link time* means that the client library must present exactly the same interface as the original library. This includes, to the extent that they are widely used, any undocumented features of the original implementation that manifest themselves as symbols that require link-time resolution. Building a client-library requires great understanding of the existing implementation as well as current use of the target API.

To build a good data server for files or data sets encoded using an API it is important to understand the data model(s) the API supports and how they relate to the DODS data models. Each of the various data types that the API supports must be translated into a DODS data type (i.e., one of the DODS classes that descend from *BaseType*). However, there is often not a one-to-one match between the API's types and the DODS types. Thus, the data server author must decide how to best translate the API's types into DODS types so as to preserve as much of the data set author's intent. This is exacerbated by the use of various conventions that (implicitly) bind several variables together with a data set. When this pattern shows up (as it does with NetCDF) you must decide whether to lump all variables together that *appear* to use the convention (and thus falsely group some variables) or to group only those which actually are explicitly grouped using whatever the API provides. If you choose the latter then any data sets which follow the convention will lose information. When building the data server it is important to keep such tradeoffs in mind.

The following sections discuss the specifics of building a data server and a client library. The existing NetCDF server and client library are used as examples. Many APIs are very similar in their overall organization. The source code used

for these examples can be found in `$(DODS_ROOT)/src/nc-dods/`. Much of the NetCDF example will be relevant to your task, even if your target API is significantly different. The `$(DODS_ROOT)/src/jg-dods/` directory contains both a data server and client library for the Joint Geophysical Ocean Flux Study relational data system.

4.1 Data Servers

The DODS data server consists of a *dispatch* program and a set of *filter* programs. The dispatch program reads the incoming URL and decides which of the filter programs to run based on the URL suffix.

A typical DODS data request uses three filters: one to return the *DAS* (*.das*), one for the *DDS* (*.dds*), and the third for the data (*.dods*). A client can also request ASCII data (*.asc* or *.ascii*), usage information about the server (*.info*), or version information about the server and the data (*.ver*).

The task of building a DODS server can then be separated into the following steps:

- ❶ Create concrete classes of the entire *BaseType* hierarchy, with `read` functions for each data type. Certain APIs cannot handle certain DODS types. For these types, there must still be a concrete class, but it can have a `read` method with a null body.
- ❷ Write functions that use the native API to extract from the dataset the information needed to build the DODS *DAS* and *DDS* objects, and then build them with the methods those classes provide.

NOTE: This step has nothing at all to do with DODS. This is between you and your data. DODS makes no demands on how these structures are created. That is, for example, if all the data to be served has the same DDS, feel free to cheat. The only thing that is important is that the structures accurately reflect the relationships of the data.

- ❸ Create filter programs to return the *DAS*, *DDS*, data, and server usage and version information.
- ❹ Create a dispatch program to parse an incoming URL and invoke the correct filter program.

To install the finished server, put the filter programs into a web server's CGI directory, and put the datasets to be served somewhere they can be seen by those filter programs. Refer to the *The DODS User Guide* for more details about installing a server.

4.1.1 The Dispatch CGI

The DODS dispatch CGI program receives a data request from the DODS client, and dispatches the request to one of several filter programs. The dispatch CGI is

stored in a CGI directory on the host machine. Its name is an important detail of its operation. The name should begin with `nph-`, and end with the letters that distinguish data files containing data formatted with that API from other files.¹ So, for example, NetCDFdata files are called `foo.nc`, so the NetCDFdispatch CGI is called `nph-nc`.

The dispatch CGI's job is to parse the incoming URL and execute the appropriate filter programs with the arguments enclosed in the URL. The dispatch CGI is also be responsible for the first level of error information that must be returned to the user. These tasks are easily accomplished in any scripting language. On the off chance you wish to use Perl, DODS provides a Perl class designed to make writing the CGI a simple task.

The file `DODS_Dispatch.pm` contains the definitions of the `DODS_Dispatch` class. This class provides several methods used to parse the incoming URL, and one method for delivering error messages to the client. The `DODS_Dispatch` provides the following methods:

command() Returns the command string implied by the input URL. The command string looks like:

command filename -e query-string.

Where *command* is the DODS filter program to be run, *filename* is the absolute filename of the dataset on which to run it, and *query-string* is the constraint expression that was enclosed in the URL. Of the `DODS_dispatch` methods, many dispatch CGI scripts may only need to use this one and `print_error_msg`. See figure 4.1

query() Returns the query string from the URL. This is the DODS constraint expression.

filename() Returns the absolute filename corresponding to the requested dataset.

extension() Returns the extension on the end of the URL. For DODS, this will be `das`, `dds`, `dods`, `info`, or `ver`.

cgi-dir() Returns the absolute pathname of the directory in which the dispatch CGI is stored. This is generally the same as the directory in which the DODS filter programs are stored.

script() Returns the name of the dispatch CGI, minus the `nph-`, and any suffixes used for a secure server.

¹The `nph-` is a relic, dating from the misty dawn of the World Wide Web and the first http standards. It stands for "Non-Parsing Header" (See the CGI 1.1 Standard for more information.), and is the only way to pass data through many httpd servers unparsed.

`print_error_message(ver)` This returns an error message to the client, explaining how to use the server. The `ver` argument should be a string containing the version of the server software. The error message returned is encoded in the `DODS_Dispatch.pm` file.

`print_help_message()` This returns a help message to the client. This can be issued in response to a confusing or inadequate URL. The help message returned is encoded in the `DODS_Dispatch.pm` file.

A sample (simple) DODS dispatch CGI is shown in figure 4.1. This is a Perl script using the `DODS_Dispatch` methods. This script assumes that all data is rooted in the http document directory subtree.²

```
#!/usr/local/bin/perl

use Env;
use DODS_Dispatch;

$dispatch = new DODS_Dispatch;

$command = $dispatch->command();

if ($command ne "") {          # if no error...
    exec($command);
} else {
    my $script_rev = '$Revision: 1.5 $ ';
    $script_rev =~ s@[A-Z]*: (.*) \@@$2@;

    $dispatch->print_error_msg($script_rev);
}
```

Figure 4.1: A simple DODS data server dispatch CGI.

4.1.2 The *DAS* and *DDS* filter programs

The simplest way to learn about creating a new filter program to return a dataset's *DAS* or *DDS* is to examine the existing filter programs. In this section, we will examine the NetCDF servers.

The source code for the *DAS* filter program distributed with the NetCDFserver software is shown in figure 4.2. The *DAS* and *DDS* filters are very similar, so only the *DAS* filter will be discussed here. The important differences between the two will be pointed out.

²You can use this even if you want to access files outside that subtree. Simply use a symbolic link and make sure that your server is set to follow symbolic links.

The CGI dispatch program makes heavy use of commonly used functions collected in the *DODS_Dispatch* class. In the same way, the *DODS_Filter* class collects several commonly used functions for the construction of filter programs. The example program uses several methods of that class. Other useful utility functions are in the `cgi-util` collection.

The filter program in figure 4.2 can be separated into the following steps:

- line 16** Step 1: The *DODS_Filter* class provides a constructor that parses the argument list to create the data. You can use the `OK` method to check that the list was parsed properly. Any errors here indicate a mistake in the dispatch CGI itself. This is why the `print_usage` function prints its message to the WWW server log file when it returns an error object to the client.
- line 21** Step 2: If the user has only requested version information from the server, it is provided here.
- line 26** Step 3: The `read_variables` function performs the real work of this program. This involves scanning the dataset itself for data variable attributes and using the *DAS* method functions to assemble the corresponding *DAS*. This operation is specific to the data access API in use, so does not make a good example.
- line 29** Step 4: Each of the filter programs must create a Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions document to hold its return value. The *DAS* and *DDS* filters return a text MIME document; they set up the MIME headers using the utility function `set_mime_text`.
- line 34** Step 5: Once the data set has been read and the attribute table built, the *DAS* ancillary file is loaded. The example filter looks for a file with the same root name as the data set and an extension of `.das`. If such a file exists, it is read in using the *DAS* member function `DAS::parse` and the information it contains is merged with the *DAS* built from the dataset.
- line 37** Step 6: Finally the *DAS* member function `print` is used to send the textual representation of the *DAS* to the client. When it is invoked by the `httpd` daemon, the dispatch CGI's standard input and output are a socket connected to the remote client process. This means that since the filter is invoked by the dispatch script, its output goes directly to the client. The *DODS_Filter* `send_das` method looks something like this:

```
DODSFilter::send_das(DAS &das)

    {
    set_mime_text(dods_das);
    das.print();

    return true;

    }
```

Note that the example filter in figure 4.2 does not use any caching. It is possible to build a more sophisticated filter program that saves the generated DAS to a text file and then uses that file without first interrogating the data set, thus saving on access. It is also possible to write a DAS by hand and *always* use that if the data set does not contain any of the type of information that the DAS has.

```
1 #include <iostream.h>
2
3 #include "DAS.h"
4 #include "cgi_util.h"
5 #include "DODSFilter.h"
6
7 extern bool read_variables(DAS &das,
8     const char *filename, String *error);
9
10 int
11 main(int argc, char *argv[])
12 {
13     DAS das;
14     DODSFilter df(argc, argv);
15
16     if (!df.OK()) {
17         df.print_usage();
18         return 1;
19     }
20
21     if (df.version()) {
22         df.send_version_info();
23         return 0;
24     }
25
26     String errMsg;
27     if(!read_variables(das, df.get_dataset_name(), &errMsg){
28         Error e(no_such_file, errMsg);
29         set_mime_text(dods_error);
30         e.print();
31         return 1;
32     }
33
34     if (!df.read_ancillary_das(das))
35         return 1;
36
37     if (!df.send_das(das))
38         return 1;
39
40     return 0;
41 }
```

Figure 4.2: The DAS filter program.

Caching *DAS* and *DDS* Objects

Because the construction of the *DAS* and *DDS* objects requires that an entire data set be scanned, it can become very inefficient to continually rebuild these objects. Because the *DAS* and *DDS* filter programs use a text representation for transmission from the server to the client, it is simple to store both the *DAS* and *DDS* objects once they have been created. Subsequent accesses to these objects can be accomplished by reading and transmitting the textual representation without actually building the binary data object.

When taking advantage of this optimization, it is important that the server check the date stamp of the *DAS/DDS* text objects and compare it to the latest modification date of the data set. For any dataset to which new data is periodically added, the *DAS/DDS* text object must clearly be updated so that the cached text object matches exactly the object that would be created if the object were built by querying the data set.

The update of the *DAS/DDS* text object can itself be optimized significantly. It is not actually necessary to completely re-read the entire data set. Because the software used to build both the *DAS* and the *DDS* binary objects work incrementally, it is possible to read text version of the *DAS/DDS* object, and then read only the new parts of the data set. The binary object will be added to as needed.

NOTE: The *DAS/DDS* software may not properly update *changed* data (data that was present in a previous version of the data set, but is now different) nor is it straightforward to remove data which is no longer present in the data set. In these cases it is usually better to regenerate the *DAS/DDS* from scratch.

4.1.3 The Data filter

The data filter program is structured similarly to both the *DAS* and *DDS* filters except that it returns a binary MIME document rather than text and that it takes two arguments instead of just one. In addition to the data set or file name (argument 1) it also takes the *DODS* constraint expression (argument 2, which was enclosed in the URL's *query*).

The NetCDF data filter is all but identical to the *DDS* filter. The only difference is that it calls the `send_data` method of *DODSFilter* to send the binary data over the network. This function calls the *DDS* `send` method.

If for some reason you cannot use the `send` member function of *DDS*, then you must ensure that the `read`, `CE evaluation` and the `serialize` operations are all carried out in the correct order. Furthermore, you must ensure that the return value of the data filter is a binary MIME document with a text prefix (currently, *DODS*

does not use the multi-part MIME standard); that is a regular binary MIME document with a section at the start that is text. This text is the *DDS* generated after evaluating the projection clauses of the constraint expression. The text part is separated from the data by the keyword “Data:” at the start of the line.³

The ASCII Data Filter

DODS is packaged with a filter to translate a DODS data stream into an ASCII data file. Clients can request ASCII data by appending `.asc` or `.ascii` to their URL instead of `.dods`. The `asciival` program is useful as a standalone client (see *The DODS User Guide*), but may also be used by a server to provide ASCII data.

A request for ASCII data is processed as any other request for data, but the final output of the data filter is piped into the `asciival` program and the result returned to the client:

```
nc_dods Data.nc | asciival -m -- -
```

The `DODS_Dispatch` class takes care of this step automatically, when it encounters a request using `.asc` or `.ascii`.

4.1.4 The Usage Filter

Client requests containing a `.info` suffix should return to the client HTML text containing documentation of both the server usage and the dataset named in the query. DODS provides a `usage` filter that can be used for this purpose. The `DODS_Dispatch` class invokes this filter.

The DODS-provided `usage` filter accepts two arguments, the data file name requested and the name of the CGI script (the dispatch CGI) in use:

```
usage filename CGI-name
```

The `usage` filter looks in the dataset directory for a file called `filename.html`, and in the directory specified in the `CGI-name` argument for a file called `CGI-name.html`. These two files must contain HTML, but without the `<html>`, `<head>`, or `<body>` tags.

For example, suppose a dispatch CGI using the `DODS_Dispatch` class receives a URL like this:

```
http://dods/cgi-bin/nph-nc/data.info
```

In this case, the `usage` filter looks for two files: `cgi-bin/nph-nc.html` and `data.html` (the `htdocs` directory is assumed in the second case). The contents of

³The “Data:” keyword is not in the scope of the text *DDS* so it is possible to have the text `Data:` in the *DDS*.

these two files are concatenated with an HTML representation of the *DAS* and *DDS* for the `data.nc` file, and the whole thing is returned to the client. If the HTML files are not found, the returned document contains only the *DAS* and *DDS*.

4.1.5 Documenting Your Work

If you do write a server, and intend to circulate it beyond your own site, here are some guidelines for documenting that server that will help others use it.

Since there are two sets of “users” for a data server program, there are two sets of instructions that need to be prepared for a given server. One set will be read by the person who installs and maintains the server on the host platform. The other set is designed to be read by people who intend to request data from that server. These users will get this documentation by submitting queries to the Info Service, in rather the same way that many UNIX commands have a `-usage` option.

In addition to these two documents, all servers should include a set of text files in their distribution directory.

The README File

The README file should contain the following information:

- A brief overview that describes the purpose and method of operation of the server.
- The revision level of the server.
- Any features the local `httpd` daemon must support to use this server.
- Any data translations that this data server can do. If any are done, they should be described in detail, so that users can know what data they get.

The ERRORS File

The ERRORS file should contain a complete list of the error messages and explanations that might ever be issued by the server.

Installation Notes

These instructions should be included in a file called `INSTALL` which is to be included with the server distribution. At a minimum, they should cover the following topics:

- Configuring and compiling the server code. Ideally, there should be a `configure` script included, but detailed instructions on editing the `Makefile` will often suffice. Remember to install the usage data file somewhere the server can find it.
- Are there any environment variables that must be defined in order to run the server? Are there other programs (e.g. `gzip`) that must be installed on the host machine?
- What configuration options are there for the installed server? This covers issues like enabling data compression, ancillary data caching, and choosing the GUI manager program with which the server will communicate. If there are performance trade-offs associated with each option, note them here.
- Ancillary data files:
 - Must the installer prepare ancillary data files by hand, or are these created automatically and cached?
 - If they must be created, where ought they be put?
 - If they are cached, where are they kept?
 - Also, if the ancillary data files are cached, what implications are there for updating the data sets served by this server? (i.e. must the ancillary data files be updated also? Deleted and recreated?)
- What temporary files will be created by the server? Where will they be stored? Under what conditions may (or must they) they be erased?

Information Files

The information files contain the information that remote users of this server will use to figure out how to use this server and its datasets once it is installed somewhere. The files are used in constructing the HTML page for the `info` server. The `.info` results can include information about both the server and the current dataset. (In fact, the results will usually include the DAS and DDS of the dataset named in the URL.)

When a user appends `.info` to a URL, the info service is activated. This service collates information about the server and the dataset (from the DAS, DDS, lists of global attributes, and variable summaries), and assembles that information in an HTML document. The server then looks for additional HTML files created by the server's administrator, and appends them the original file, and returns the whole document to the client.

Although it is possible merely to rely on the collated data to describe a server, we hope that server writers will provide rich, human-friendly descriptions of the server's usage and the accompanying datasets. These files can be thought of as "usage" or "README" files. At a minimum, they should cover:

- Any special data functions defined by the server that can be used in a constraint expression, and
- Any data model translations the server supports, and how they are to be controlled by the user⁴
- A list of the programs a user should have to use certain features of the server. For example, note here that the server expects that the GUI manager is running a Tcl interpreter.
- A list of the error messages that the user is apt to see. Include explanations of the conditions that may have caused them, and any steps the user may take to recover from them.
- The answers to any questions you are frequently asked about this server or its usage.

The usage data file need not be any more elaborate than any man page.

To create information for a server, write an HTML fragment using the format given below, and put the HTML file in the same directory as the server. Name it using the base name of the server; for example, the HTML file that describes the netCDF server (made up of `nph-nc`, and `nc_das`, `nc_dods` and so on) is called `nc.html`.

This example shows the correct HTML tagging for server information:

```
<h3>
Server Function:
</h3>
<dl>
<dt>geolocate(variable, lat1, lat2, lon1, lon2)</dt>
<dd>Returns the elements of <em>variable</em> that fall
within the box created by (<em>lat1</em>,<em>lon1</em>)
and (<em>lat2</em>,<em>lon2</em>).</dd>
<p>
<dt>time(variable, start_time, stop_time)</dt>
<dd>Returns the elements of <em>variable</em> that fall
within the time interval <em>start_time</em> and
<em>stop_time</em>.</dd>
</dl>
<p>
```

For datasets, put the HTML file, tagged using the format given below, in the same directory as the datasets. Name it using the base name of the datasets; for

⁴Remember that the “how” is to be answered very specifically, and on the user’s level (i.e. “Do such-and-such, spelled like *this*, to make the array returned be nx5 instead of 5xn.”), and not on the programmer’s level (i.e. “You use the invert method to return an array of 5xn instead of nx5.”)

example, the HTML file for `fnoc1.nc`, `fnoc2.nc`, and `fnoc3.nc` might be called `fnoc.html`. This example shows the correct HTML for a dataset information file:

```
<h3>
About the dataset
</h3>
This is where the server administrator would supply
information about the dataset. And so on...
<p>
```

You may prefer to override this method of creating documentation and simply provide a single, complete HTML document that contains general information for the server or for a group of datasets. For example, to force the info server to return a particular HTML document for all its datasets, you would create a complete HTML document and give it the name `dataset.ovr`, where `dataset` is the dataset name. The HTML file in this case would look like this:

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Override document</title>
</head>
<body>
<h2>
Test dataset
</h2>
This is where the server administrator would supply
information about the dataset(s) and what-have-you.
</body>
</html>
```

Remember to ensure that the installation instructions cover installing the usage data file in a place where the server can find it.

4.2 Client Libraries

The goal of building a client library is to provide a drop-in replacement for an existing API so that user programs written for that API can switch to the DODS version and access remote DODS data. The user programs should not require any modification to change over to the DODS client library version of the API. However, the API will clearly need substantial changes to its current implementation.

In order to build the DODS client library for a particular API, it is useful to divide the API to be re-implemented into five categories of functions:

- Open or connect
- Variable information read
- Data read
- Write
- Close or disconnect

4.2.1 Rewriting the Open and Close Functions

The functions that perform the dataset “open” and “close” operations must be implemented so that information about the data set can be retrieved from the data server. These functions must store the necessary state information so that subsequent accesses for variable information or data reads can be satisfied. This state information will, in almost every case, be the dataset’s *DAS* and *DDS*.

The open function for a DODS client library version of a given API must first determine if the data object (typically a file) is local to the user program making the open call or is a remote data object to be accessed through DODS. It is possible to access DODS objects which are local to a user program, but there is little reason to do so if the data object can also be accessed through the original API. In any case, the distinction of local or remote is made on the basis whether a URL is used to reference the data object, or a local filename.

If the data object is remote, then the open function must build a structure which can hold the *DAS* and *DDS* objects which describe the named data set. This is the *Connect* class object. Once this object is built, the open function must map this structure to a file identifier or pointer which can be passed back to the user program as the return value of the open function. You add this data to the *Connect* objects when you sub-class them for a particular API. Subsequent accesses to the data set will include this identifier (or pointer), and each function that is a member of the API can be modified to use it to gain access to the state information stored by the open function.

The close function should use the state information accessible with the file identifier or pointer returned by the open function to determine if the dataset is local or remote. In the case of a local data set, the original implementation's close function must be called. In the case of a remote data set, the locally stored state information must be freed. You can do this by destroying the *Connect* object.

See Section 3.2 on page 24 for an example of a recoded open function and a description of its use. (The example uses the NetCDF API.)

4.2.2 Getting Information about Variables

Most APIs for self-describing data sets include functions which return information about the variables that comprise a data set. These functions return information about the type and shape of variables in a form that can be used by a program as well as attribute information about the variables that is more often than not intended for use by humans. Each of these functions must be rewritten so that to the extent possible, information present in the *DAS* and *DDS* is used to satisfy them.

While many 'self-describing' APIs may have dozens of these functions, the basic structure of the re-implemented code is the same for each one. If the data set is local, use the original implementation, otherwise use the locally stored state information (*DAS* and *DDS*) to answer the request for data.

Rewriting these functions can be the most labor intensive part of re-implementing a given API. This is typically the largest group of functions in the API and the information stored in the *DAS* and *DDS* must often be 'massaged' before it fulfills the specifications of the API. Thus the rewritten functions must not only get the necessary information from the *DAS* and *DDS* objects, but they must also transform the types of the objects used to return that information to the user program into the data types the program expects.

4.2.3 Reading the Values of Variables from a Dataset

To read data values from a dataset using a typical data access API, a user would submit to some API function the name of the variable to be read. The DODS client library version of this same function must take that variable name and use it to construct a constraint expression. (See Section 4.3.2 for more information on using constraint expressions to access data.) The constraint expression must then be appended to the dataset URL (with the suffix *.dods*), and the resulting URL sent out into the internet.

For example, to get a variable called *var* from a dataset at:

```
http://blah/cgi-bin/nph-nc/weekly.nc.dods
```

you would use the URL:

```
http://blah/cgi-bin/nph-nc/weekly.nc.dods?var
```

The *Connect* class contains a member function, `request_data` that performs this task. It takes the constraint expression and the suffix to use for requesting data, appends them to the *Connect* URL, and sends the entire string off to retrieve its corresponding data.

The `request_data` function returns a pointer to a *DDS* object, which contains the data as well as the structure description corresponding to the data request.

Once the `request_data` member function has returned, the client library must still call the `deserialize` member function (which is part of the DODS Type Classes) for each returned variable. The client library should use the variable objects contained in the *DDS* object returned by `request_data` to invoke the `deserialize` member function. Once that is done, the data values are stored in the internal buffers of the variable objects in the new *DDS*⁵. The client library should store this new *DDS*, along with the constraint expression passed to `request_data` so that future requests by the user program for the same information can be handled without accessing the remote data server.

The data values of variables in a *DDS* are accessed using the `buf2val` member function for the cardinal and vector types and by accessing the values of fields for constructor types.

Translation

For a DODS client library to be robust, it may have to be equipped to deal with data types it was not designed to use. For example, the NetCDF software cannot manipulate a DODS Sequence. But a user can use the DODS version of the NetCDF library to request data from a server that provides Sequence data. When cases like this arise (and they arise fairly often), the author of the client library must choose an appropriate data type into which the served data is to be translated, and implement functions to do that translation.

Often, translation from one data type to another is a simple task. Translating an Array into Sequence format is fairly straightforward, although there are several ways to do it. (The author of the client library should choose one, and document that choice in a README file.)

Other translations are more complex, and may even require that the client library violate the semantics of the original API, or of one of the DODS data types. For example, translating a Sequence to an Array in NetCDF requires that the client know in advance the length of the Sequence, which is not necessarily known.

⁵For the *Sequence* data type, the *DDS* contains only the current instance of the data. Repeated calls to the *Sequence*'s `deserialize` function are required to return successive instances of the sequence.

4.2.4 Functions that Write to Data Sets

DODS is a read-only data system. While it is not technically inconceivable, a system which allows modification of remote data sets would be operationally much more complex than DODS. Thus, functions that write data are rewritten so that they call the original implementation in the case of a local access or return an error code in the case of a remote access. The error code should indicate a recoverable error so that programs which perform both reads and writes can recover if their logic permits.

4.2.5 Adding Local Access to a DODS Client Library

In order to ensure that programs, once they have been re-linked with DODS client libraries, can still access local data files it is necessary to add software to read those local data to the functions in the re-implemented library. Typically in each function in the new library the state information accessed by the identifier passed to the function is used to determine if the call is to access local or remote data. In the former case, the function must do exactly what the original implementation of the API would have done to satisfy the function call.

It is wasteful to completely recode the entire API just to achieve local access. However, it is also not possible to simply link the user program with both the DODS client library and the original library. because both libraries must *define the same external symbols*. Linking with both libraries will produce link-time conflicts on most computers or result in an incorrectly linked binary image.

In order to use the original implementation of the library, you must rename all of its external symbols that will appear in user programs. For example, if an API defines four functions (**open**, **close**, **read** and **write**) and one global variable (**errno**), then each of those must be renamed to some new symbol (e.g., **orig_open**, **orig_close**, ...). These source modules can then be added to the set of object modules used to build the DODS client library. Of course the DODS client library must also include the original external symbol names; one approach is to recode each of the APIs external symbols as a function which either calls the DODS-replacement or the original function (now renamed so that the symbols do not conflict) depending on whether the access is local or remote.

4.3 Using Constraints

Constraint expressions are an important part of DODS, providing a powerful way to control how data is accessed without forcing the Data Access Protocol to support a lot of different messages. Constraint expressions are used to select which variables will be extracted from a data set by both the user and by the client library. The constraint expression syntax is described in detail in the *The DODS User Guide*.

4.3.1 How Constraint Expressions are Evaluated

The server-side constraint expressions are evaluated using a two step process. Every constraint expression has two parts, the projection and the selection subexpressions. The projection part of a constraint expression tells which variables to include in any return document describing the data set and the selection subexpression limits the returned data to variables with values that satisfy a set of relational expressions. The projection subexpression is evaluated when the entire constraint expression is parsed; at parse-time the server's copy of the data set's *DDS* is marked with the variables included in the projection. The selection subexpression, however, is not evaluated until values are read from the data set. One way to classify the projection and selection subexpressions is that projections depend solely on the logical structure of a data set, while selections depend on the values of particular variables within that data set.

4.3.2 Different Ways of Using Constraint Expressions

There are two different ways that constraint expressions can be used. One is by the client library and the other is by the user. When writing a client library that has features for selecting variables or parts of variables, try to code the replacements to those calls so that they build up DODS constraint expressions that will request only the data the user wants. Then read the data from the returned *DDS* and store it in the variable(s) passed to the API call by the user. This is a much better solution than requesting the entire variable from the data set and then throwing away parts of it.

Suppose that the user program (via the API's functional interface) asks for the data in variable *X*. The constraint expression that will retrieve *X* is simply '*X*'. Suppose, given the following *DDS* that the user program requests the two variables *u* and *v* from the embedded structure.

```

Dataset {
  Int32 u[time_a = 16][lat = 17][lon = 21];
  Int32 v[time_a = 16][lat = 17][lon = 21];
  Float64 lat[lat = 17];
  Float64 lon[lon = 21];
  Float64 time[time = 16];
} fnoc1;

```

A constraint expression that would project just those variables would be `fnoc1.u,fnoc1.v`. To restrict the arrays `u` and `v` to only the first two dimensions (`time` and `lat`), the projection subexpression would be:

```
fnoc1.u[0:15][0:16],fnoc1.v[0:15][0:16]
```

Both of these constraint expressions have null selection subexpressions. Note that the comma operator separates the two clauses of the projection subexpression. Also note that whitespace is ignored by the constraint expression parser. See the grammar for CEs in the *The DODS User Guide* for more information about constraint expression grammar and the kind of things that can be done with the projection subexpression.

The user program may have an interface that provides the user with a way to request only certain values be returned. This is particularly true for APIs such as JGOFS that support access to relational data sets. Suppose the following *DDS* describes a relational data set:

```

Dataset {
  Sequence {
    Int32 id;
    Float64 lat;
    Float64 lon;
    Sequence {
      Float64 depth;
      Float64 temperature;
    } xbt;
  } site;
} cruise;

```

To request data with a certain range of latitude and longitude values, you can use a selection subexpression like this:

```
& lat>=10.0 & lat<=20.0 & long>=5.5 & long<=7.5
```

Note that each clause of the selection subexpression begins with a `&` and that the clauses are combined using a boolean *and*. Finally, using the previous *DDS*, if a user requested only depth and temperature given the above latitude and longitude range (i.e., the user program requests that only the depth and temperature values be returned given a certain latitude and longitude range) the client library would use the following constraint expression:

```
site.xbt.depth, site.xbt.temp & lat>=10.0 & lat<=20.0 &
long>=5.5 & long<=7.5
```

A second way that constraint expressions can be used is that users may specify an initial URL with a constraint expression already attached. In this case the `request_data` member function will append the constraint expression built by the client library to the one supplied by the user and request data constrained by both expressions. From the standpoint of a client library (or a data server, for that matter) there is no difference between a URL supplied with an initial constraint and one supplied without one.

5

Linking Your Program

To link a user program to the DODS client-library version of a data access API library, you need only substitute the name of the reimplemented API library for the original, and add the DODS Data Access Protocol library (`libdap++`) to the link list.

Because the DAP library and the API have circular dependencies they must each be included on the linker command line twice. An example of this can be seen in the DODS-NetCDF Makefile; the value of `LIBS` is passed to the linker `ld`. Note that the API library is listed first.

```
LIBS = -lnc-dods -ldap++ -lnc-dods -ldap++
```

You should have users link their programs using `gcc` or `g++` since the libraries are all built using those tools. In particular, `g++` includes `libstdc++` (and `libg++`) by default when it builds an executable program from object modules. If you use `gcc` instead of `g++` when you link, be sure to include these libraries as well after all the libraries listed above. If you don't use `gcc`, but instead use the linker directly (i.e., you call `ld` yourself) you are on your own - you can use `gcc -V` to determine what flags and additional libraries it uses that are specific to your system and then experiment with those. We cannot tell you how to proceed since each UNIX variant requires different flags and libraries.

A

Overview of the DODS Server Architecture

This appendix describes in functional terms the operation of a server.

Note that descriptions of server outputs naturally and unavoidably refer to certain kinds of inputs and vice versa. This makes it difficult to create definitions without forward and backward cross-references. Please be prepared to read this specification with a thumb between the pages as you flip back and forth from the output to the input sections.

A.1 Outputs

A server sends to a client one of three different sorts of messages:

- HTML;
- ASCII data; or
- Binary data.

A.1.1 HTML Data

There are three different kinds of HTML data returned by a DODS server. Clients that request these data should be prepared to display the HTML to the user.

Server Information (usage) One kind of HTML data is returned in response to a request for server information (using the `.info` URL suffix), and contains usage information for the server, including a formatted version of the dataset DAS and DDS. This information is formatted by the `usage` service program, invoked by the server.

WWW Interface The forms-based DODS WWW interface returns HTML data to the client. This can either be a form a user can use to create a DODS constraint expression or a DODS directory listing, depending on whether the URL indicates a file with the `.html` suffix, or a directory containing other files.

Error messages A badly formed URL will result in a DODS error message, which is simply some HTML text describing the supported URL suffixes. (See `DODS_Dispatch.pm`.) Note that though an error message could in theory be returned to any client, whether or not they can display HTML, in practice, only web browser clients are prone to these kinds of errors. Aside from web browser clients (e.g. Netscape), the DODS clients issue their server requests through the DODS client core libraries, which format the URL according to the DODS conventions.

NOTE: There are two kinds of DODS error messages. The particular one described above is issued in response to a badly formed URL. Other kinds of errors are returned as ASCII data within a DODS data document. See Section A.1.3 on page 53.

A.1.2 ASCII Data (Text)

These are the different kinds of ASCII data returned by a fully-equipped DODS server. (“Fully equipped” implies that the server has, on its execution path, all the supported DODS service programs.)

DDS The DODS Data Descriptor Structure is a description of the data contained in the dataset. It contains information about the data types and names represented in the dataset. Programmers can think of the DDS as containing the type declarations for the data. The DDS is fully described in *The DODS User Guide*. The DDS is created with a service program called `*_dds`, where the `*` is the same two-letter abbreviation used in the server name (`nph-*`).

DAS The DODS Data Attribute Structure contains information *about* the data in the dataset—the metadata. It is a hierarchical list of name-type-value triples, where the names of the containers correspond to entries in the DDS. The DAS is fully described in *The DODS User Guide*. The DAS is created with a service program called `*_das`, where the `*` is the same two-letter abbreviation used in the server name (`nph-*`).

ASCII Data If a DODS server is equipped with a service program called `asciival`, it can convert binary data to ascii data on the fly, allowing you to use a standard web browser (such as Netscape) to examine data. This feature can also be used to import data into a client that may not be able to process DODS data encoded in the standard binary format.

A.1.3 Binary Data

The DODS data document consists of two parts, a DDS describing the data returned, and the data itself. It may also consist of ASCII data describing an error condition.

DDS The DDS returned with the data differs slightly from the DDS returned by a simple request using the `.dds` URL suffix. Whereas the DDS returned in response to that URL is a description of the dataset available, the DDS returned in a data document describes the data being returned. If you ask for an entire dataset, there will be no difference between these two DDS's. However, if you request only a *part* of a dataset, the DDS included in the data document will only reflect the part of the dataset returned to you.

As an example, consider a dataset containing an array with one hundred elements. The DDS for this dataset will contain an array with one hundred elements. However, if you send a server a request for just the first fifty elements of the array, the DODS data document returned will contain a DDS with only fifty elements. This is illustrated in figure A.1.

Data The data requested from a server is (unsurprisingly) also contained in the DODS server's response to a data request. The data is encoded using the XDR standard (eXternal Data Representation), and packed into the second part of the response document. For more information on XDR, see Internet RFC 1014. For further details, see Section A.1.3 on page 55, below.

Error Messages A DODS data document may contain an error message. This is a DODS Error object (containing an ASCII error message and some other data) stuck into the HTTP document where the data would usually go. This is where error conditions on the server are noted, as well as badly formed constraint expressions and file names.

Figure A.1: The DODS Data Document and the DDS. For the dataset containing the vector `temp`, with 100 elements, the top “Simple DDS Request” shows what the DDS might look like for that dataset. The bottom “DODS Data Document” shows what might be returned by a request for all the even-numbered elements of the `temp` array. Note that the DDS has been altered to allow for the reduced number of elements in the returned data array.

The HTTP response containing the DODS data document is formatted like this:

```
HTTP/1.0 200 OK
XDODS-Server: <server/dap version string>
Content-type: application/octet-stream
Content-Description: dods-data
Content-Encoding: deflate
<blank line>
<DDS>
Data:
<binary data, each variable given in the order it is listed
in the DDS>
<EOF>
```

Note the following:

- DODS servers use HTTP 1.0.
- The version string (after the `XDODS-Server:` header) must be `⌈text⌋/⌈version number⌋` where version number is `x.y` or `x.z.y`. This version number is parsed on the client side to ensure that a client is communicating with a compatible server.
- The `Content-Encoding` is used only when the document is compressed using 'deflate'. (This is the same as the compression used by the `gzip` program, and is implemented in `libz.a`.)
- `Content-Description` is used by the DODS client to figure out if the object is an error instead of a data object. If it is, the `Content-Description` field should read `dods-error`.

Encoding the DAP Data Types

The DODS transmission protocol separates variables into three classes: scalars, arrays, and sequences. A scalar is included in the DODS data document simply by writing its XDR representation. An array is sent by writing the number of elements (as an XDR `int`) followed by the elements themselves, also in the XDR format. However, arrays of `Byte`, `Int16`, `Int32`, `UInt16`, `UInt32`, `Float32`, and `Float64` actually have their size sent twice, once by the DAP software and once by the XDR software. Here's a hex dump of some `Int32` array data that shows this behavior:

```

00000000: 4461 7461 7365 7420 7b0a 2020 2020 496e Dataset { . In
00000010: 7433 3220 755b 7469 6d65 5f61 203d 2031 t32 u[time_a = 1
00000020: 5d5b 6c61 7420 3d20 315d 5b6c 6f6e 203d ][lat = 1][lon =
00000030: 2032 315d 3b0a 7d20 666e 6f63 313b 0a44 21];.} fnoc1;.D
00000040: 6174 613a 0a00 0000 1500 0000 15ff fff9 ata:.....
00000050: 40ff fff6 6fff fff3 e5ff fff1 ffff fff3 @...o.....
00000060: 4aff fff6 9aff fffb 1c00 0002 9600 0009 J.....
00000070: b300 000b 5e00 000b 0300 000b 8200 000a .....^.....
00000080: b900 000a ae00 000b 7300 000a 2900 0008 .....s...)...
00000090: 5b00 0007 3500 0006 da00 0007 6900 0007 [...5.....i...
000000a0: 3e >

```

The length bytes for the ;data; section start at address 0x45 (The length is 0x00000015.) and is repeated at 0x49. Here's how you can see this:

```
geturl "http://dods.gso.uri.edu/cgi-bin/nph-nc/data/fnoc1.nc?u[0:0][0:0][0:20]"
```

The DDS for this dataset is (use `geturl -d`):

```

Dataset {
  Int32 u[time_a = 16][lat = 17][lon = 21];
  Int32 v[time_a = 16][lat = 17][lon = 21];
  Float64 lat[lat = 17];
  Float64 lon[lon = 21];
  Float64 time[time = 16];
} fnoc1;

```

Structures and Grids are sent by serializing their components, one by one, in the order of their declaration in the DDS.

Sequences have a much more complex encoding scheme because one sequence may contain another sequence *and* because the sequence type provides no information about the length of a given instance. To send sequences the DAP uses two different algorithms, one up to DODS version 2.14 servers and clients and a better (more compact one) after that. DODS clients at version 2.15 and later can all read from both servers *but* they assume that a server that does not announce its version is very old and will attempt to read Sequences using the old algorithm. (So if you're writing a new DODS server that serves Sequences, you must remember to address the version requirement.)

Here's how the new algorithm encodes a sequence:

- ❶ Serialize row of the sequence by:
 - ❶ Writing the start of instance marker (0x5A), and
 - ❷ Serializing (writing the XDR encoding of) each element in the row in the order of appearance, then
- ❷ Write the end of sequence marker (0x5A).

A.2 Inputs

The input to a DODS server is contained in an HTTP “GET” request. Unlike a POST, the information in this kind of request is all in the URL. Consequently, examining the parts of a DODS URL will illustrate all the different sorts of requests a DODS server can handle.

Figure A.2 contains a description of the parts of a DODS URL, not including the “Constraint Expression.” The constraint expression and the parts of the DODS URL are described in detail in *The DODS User Guide* and *The DODS User Guide*.

<i>Protocol</i>	<i>MachineName</i>	<i>Server</i>	<i>Directory</i>	<i>Filename</i>	<i>URLSuffix</i>
http	://dods.gso.uri.edu	/cgi-bin/nph-nc	/data	/fnoc1.nc	.das

Figure A.2: Parts of a DODS URL (without a constraint expression)

A.2.1 Request types

A DODS server is equipped to respond to several different request types. Each request type is signified by a different URL suffix. The server itself is just a dispatch script, that determines the type of a request, and dispatches the request to the appropriate service program, and relays its result back to the client.

In figure A.3, a DODS client makes a GET request to a DODS server (which is just an `httpd` daemon equipped with a bunch of CGI programs). The daemon invokes the DODS Server, which is a simple-minded dispatch script which in turn invokes the DAS, DDS, Data, or other service program.

The request types, their suffixes, and the service programs are listed in table A.1.

A.2.2 Constraint expressions

A DODS server can accept a “constraint expression” contained in the URL query string. The DODS constraint expression describes how a DODS server should subsample a DODS dataset before sending the data back to the client. The details of the constraint expression syntax are covered in *The DODS User Guide*.

What’s important here is simply that the constraint expression is a logical expression with two clauses: projection and selection.

The “projection” clause of a constraint expression specifies the data variables requested by the client, and the “selection” clause specifies the condition under which the client wants them. That is, the projection clause might specify that the client wants to see oceanic temperature data, and the selection clause would specify that only records from below 1000 meters should be returned.

Figure A.3: The Architecture of a DODS Data Server.

Table A.1: Table of URL suffixes.

Suffix	Service Program	Description
.dds	*_dds	Returns the Data Descriptor Structure for the specified dataset.
.das	*_das	Returns the Data Attribute Structure for the specified dataset.
.dods	*_dods	Returns binary data in the form of a DODS data document. See Section A.1.3 on page 53.
.asc	asciival	Converts data requests to ASCII values before sending them back to the client. This service is useful for invoking from simple web browsers.
.info	usage	Returns an HTML formatted version of the dataset DDS and DAS, and any other server and dataset information provided in *.ovr files.
.html	none	Returns a URL constraint expression builder form, based on the dataset DDS and DAS. This is the DODS WWW interface.
.ver	none	Returns the server version information.

A.2.3 Server functions

Within the context of a constraint expression, a server can implement functions a client would use to specify data. Since the constraint expression has two kinds of clauses, there are two kinds of server functions: projection and selection.

To implement another server-side constraint function, see . Following is a list of the canonical server-side functions implemented in all DODS servers.

Selection

yes

Projection

yes

B

Overview of the DODS Client

A DODS client is any web client that makes a service request to a DODS server. Since several of the DODS services return ASCII and HTML data, any web browser, such as Netscape Navigator can be considered a DODS client, so long as it is in the process of making a suitable request to a DODS server. The clients of interest in this appendix, however, are clients that use the DODS DAP (Data Access Protocol) library to make their requests for data.

Of these clients, there are two varieties: clients that have been written expressly for DODS, and clients that existed in some form already, and that have been adapted to use with a DODS client library.

Figure B.1: The Original Program, untouched by DODS. The application's code accesses data by calls to the netCDF library functions, linked with the program. Data access is direct, with the application program accessing local disk files to read data.

Figure B.2: The Modified Program, using the DODS netCDF client library. The application's code now accesses data by calls to the DODS netCDF library functions. These are written to be functionally identical to the original netCDF functions, but instead of using a local disk to retrieve data, this library invokes functions from the DODS DAP library, which makes HTTP GET requests to a DODS server. The client code is unchanged.

Figure B.3: Another Way. An application program can also call the DODS DAP directly, eliminating the need for a client library. When starting from scratch, this is probably easiest, unless you are an old hand at one of the supported data access APIs.